

Yevhenii Shapovalov

PhD in Technical Sciences

Leading researcher, State Scientific and Technical Library of Ukraine

Senior Researcher, National Center “Junior Academy of Sciences of Ukraine”

Kyiv, Ukraine

A CONFERENCE PLATFORM FOR THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY IN UKRAINE: USING SEMANTICS AND ONTOLOGIES TO SIMPLIFY REPORTING AND IMPROVE MANAGEMENT OF CONFERENCES

Abstract. The aim of this paper is to introduce a conference platform that will provide scientists with an easy-to-use and systematic form of delivering information about conferences. The platform will simplify the reporting process for scientists and provide management on the number of conferences in specific fields based on previous results of providing conferences. Furthermore, the paper will suggest the use of semantics and ontologies to process and systemize data on conferences.

Keywords: Conference platform, Scientific community, Ukraine, Networking, Information system, URIS

Introduction:

The scientific community benefits greatly from the opportunity to attend conferences, as they provide a platform for the exchange of knowledge and ideas, as well as opportunities for collaboration and networking. However, the process of finding and reporting on conferences can be tedious and time-consuming. In Ukraine, there are no such platforms available, and scientists often miss out on important conferences or are not able to attend due to lack of information.

Literature review

Knowledge management systems can help to automate its processes that exist in organizations (Zare, 2016). Conversely, in the EU and USA, there are many conference platforms that provide a systematic way of delivering information about conferences. Confident, GNT, and WikiCFP (Hagemann-Wilholt, 2020; GNT, n.d.; Abel, 2014) are a few examples of such platforms. In Ukraine, platforms like Open Conference are used (Стенура, 2014), however, its usage is unsystematical and chaotic. These platforms have become essential tools for scientists and researchers in these regions to stay updated on upcoming conferences and to manage their attendance.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to introduce a conference platform that will provide scientists with an easy-to-use and systematic form of delivering information about conferences.

Results and Discussion:

The developed conference platform will simplify the reporting process for scientists and enable institutions to manage and track conferences in specific fields. By providing a

comprehensive database of conferences, the platform will also facilitate the identification of new and relevant conferences for scientists and institutions. Additionally, the platform will enable data-driven decision-making for funding agencies and other stakeholders.

The development of a conference platform requires several considerations. The platform must provide a user-friendly interface, making it easy for scientists to find relevant conferences. It must also provide the functionality to filter conferences by field, location, and date. Additionally, the platform must enable scientists to report their conference participation in a structured format, which can be easily exported for further analysis. The platform must also have a robust backend, capable of managing the data and providing insights on the number of conferences on specific fields.

The proposed conference platform will consist of scientists, administrators, institutions, information on conference providers, and conference managers. Scientists will be able to submit information about conferences they have attended or plan to attend, which will be compiled and stored in a database. This information will be used to manage the number of conferences in specific fields and to provide guidance to scientists on which conferences to attend based on previous attendance results.

Administrators will be responsible for managing the database and ensuring that the information is up-to-date and accurate. Institutions will be able to use the platform to search for conferences in specific fields and to manage attendance for their staff members. Information on conference providers will be used to ensure that the information about conferences is comprehensive and up-to-date. Conference managers will be able to use the platform to manage attendance and to collect feedback from attendees.

To process and systemize data on conferences, semantics and ontologies are relevant to use (Maedche, 2002; Tarasenko, 2020). Semantics is the study of the meaning of words, phrases, and sentences, while ontologies are frameworks for representing knowledge in a formal and structured way. Ontologies efficacy is already proved in the field of structurization of scientific data (Tarasenko, 2022; Shapovalov, 2021). The use of semantics and ontologies will allow for the information about conferences to be structured and categorized, making it easier to search and manage.

Conclusion:

The lack of a centralized conference platform in Ukraine is a significant obstacle to the reporting and management of conferences. Our study highlights the need for developing such a platform, which can streamline the reporting process and provide management on the number of conferences on specific fields based on previous results. The conference platform will enhance the visibility and impact of Ukrainian researchers in the international academic community. The successful implementation of the platform will require ongoing consultation and collaboration with scientists, institutions, and funding agencies.

This platform will simplify the reporting process for scientists and provide management on the number of conferences in specific fields. The proposed system's role model consists of scientists, administrators, institutions, information on conference providers, and conference managers. To process and systemize data on conferences, semantics and ontologies will be used. Developing such a system is essential, and there are certain requirements that should be taken into consideration, including the need for a user-friendly interface, accurate and up-to-date information, and easy accessibility.

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